

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

D2.4 PM training toolkit higher education certification strategy

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Project: 101108469 — PreMETS — ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO

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Deliverable:	D2.4 PM training toolkit higher education certification strategy
Work Package:	WP2: Predictive manufacturing training content development
Due Date:	M12
Submission Date:	28/06/2024
Start Date of Project:	01/07/2023
Duration of Project:	36 Months
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable:	University of Piraeus Research Center (UPRC)
Version:	1.0
Status:	Final
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Nature:	☒ R – Report P – Prototype ☐ D – Demonstrator ☐ O - Other
Dissemination level:	☒ PU – Public CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history			
Version	Date	Modified by (author/partner)	Comments
0.8	12/06/2024	Georgios Ntanis, Maria Boile / UPRC	Draft version

0.9	19/06/2024	Nemanja Zdravkovic / MUB, Ioannis Ergas / WEG	Minor Revision
1.0	28/06/2024	Georgios Ntanis / UPRC	Final version

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Section I

Course description

PreMETS is an ERASMUS+ project aiming at enhancing Predictive Maintenance (PM) practices by addressing the lack of comprehensive PM education in industry, academia, and vocational training. The whole project includes:

- the development of innovative educational toolkits for both PM learners and trainers
- the establishment of a micro-credential certification framework
- the creation of a cross-disciplinary platform integrating various PM resources
- the goal is to train:
 - 1000 PM learners
 - 250 PM trainers

In Work Package 2 (WP2) the necessary PM training content is developed. WP2 has been prepared and evaluated by the PreMETS consortium. This course aims to provide learners with the knowledge and skills to understand and apply the principles and practices of PM. In addition, the goal is set to provide adequate knowledge and assistance to trainers in order to deliver the material effectively. The following topics are covered:

- A PM training toolkit that integrates higher education EU standards. The PM training toolkit is divided into six different Workforce Needs modules (WN), covering the whole PM realm.
- Provision of a comprehensive toolkit covering an academic EQF 7 level, enhancing accessibility and effectiveness of PM education.
- Establishment of a certification system and skill validation mechanisms, offering recognition and certification for PM skills.

Trainees who successfully pass the examinations are expected to be able to apply the achieved learning outcomes at a level in line with the level of the qualification diploma. The structure of the modular course will be further described in the following paragraphs.

Competency-based learning

The modular approach is a growing trend in educational philosophy that shifts from traditional instruction to an outcome-based learning model. According to this approach, the context is divided into small, distinct, and independent units or modules that are typically brief and non-sequential. By adopting a modular approach, learners gain more control over their learning process and take on greater responsibility. This method emphasizes the importance of learner autonomy, making it particularly suitable for more mature trainees with higher perceptual capacity.

Moreover, the core principle of this approach is placing learners at the center of the teaching-learning process. Modularization demands continuous monitoring and assessment of trainees' progress throughout each module. Effective continuous assessment enables instructors to adjust their teaching methods based on assessment results. This process also provides trainees with feedback on their learning and guidance on how to improve further.

The modular approach should emphasize:

- Designing assessment tasks as integral parts of the learning process (i.e., multiple-choice questions).
- Providing feedback that supports trainees throughout their learning journey rather than only after task completion (i.e., when they receive a grade).
- Encouraging trainees to take an active role in organizing and monitoring their own learning.

Assessment involves collecting evidence and making judgments to determine whether competency has been achieved. This process confirms that an individual can perform to the standards required in the workplace, as specified in a training package, a vocational education and training (VET) or a higher education accredited course.

The modular approach allows to perform separately the assessment for each WN. Knowledge assessment will use digital assessment formats appropriate to each module, such as multiple-choice questions to assess factual knowledge. However, this requires the use of e-learning tools.

Digital tools in education

E-learning tools have transformed the education and training landscape, offering several key advantages related to accessibility and interaction:

- **Accessibility and flexibility:** E-learning tools provide convenience to the users, allowing access to training materials anytime, anywhere. This flexibility is especially beneficial for people with different locations or irregular schedules, as it allows them to learn at their own pace, whether in their business environment, school or at home.
- **Multimedia resources:** E-learning platforms offer versatility by incorporating a variety of multimedia resources such as videos, interactive simulations, and 3D models. These tools enhance the learning experience, allowing users to better understand complex processes through visual and interactive means.
- **Up-to-date context:** The material can be updated on a regular basis, and this allows students to have access to an up-to-date context anytime.

Professional profile

The course is designed for students, teachers, VET trainers, and even specialists from a cornucopia of industries (Aviation, Manufacturing, Shipping, Logistics, Transportation etc.), who want to learn more about Predictive Maintenance and how to integrate it in their business environment.

Admission requirements

In order to enroll for this course, the student needs to have completed EQF level 6, or equivalent, in a technical field of study.

Additionally, advanced knowledge of the English language is required for the successful completion of lessons, assignments and examinations.

Duration – suggested schedule

The core duration of the course is estimated to 50 contact hours with a workload of at least 124 hours of self-paced study.

Suggested self-paced schedule:

EQF Level 7: Advanced Predictive Maintenance Competences

Duration: 3 Months

Course Format: Virtual Learning Target Audience: Advanced learners, typically those with a bachelor's degree or equivalent experience in maintenance or engineering.

Month 1

Week 1-2: WN1 - Holistic PM Competences

- Title: Advanced Holistic Predictive Maintenance
- Description: In-depth exploration of integrating various competences in predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Master advanced holistic predictive maintenance principles.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Advanced booklet, video lectures, advanced maintenance software.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, complex WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Detailed exploration of holistic PM competences with advanced case studies.
- Presentation: Comprehensive overview with detailed storyboard.
- Videos: In-depth lectures on holistic predictive maintenance.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
- Assessment: WebQuest on applying advanced holistic PM skills in a complex scenario.

Week 3-4: WN2 - Digital Skills Competences for PM

- Title: Advanced Digital Skills for Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Exploration of advanced digital skills required for effective predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Develop and apply advanced digital skills in predictive maintenance contexts.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, video tutorials, advanced maintenance tools and software.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Comprehensive guide on advanced digital skills for PM.
 - Presentation: Detailed points with comprehensive storyboard.
 - Videos: Advanced tutorials on digital tools.
 - Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
 - Assessment: WebQuest focused on utilizing advanced digital tools.
-

Month 2

Week 1-2: WN3 - Green Skills Competences for PM

- Title: Advanced Sustainable Practices in Predictive Maintenance
- Description: In-depth understanding and integration of sustainable practices in predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Apply advanced green skills and sustainable practices in predictive maintenance.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, environmental impact tools, case studies, video links.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Detailed content on advanced green skills for PM.
- Presentation: Key points with comprehensive storyboard.
- Videos: In-depth lectures on sustainability in predictive maintenance.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
- Assessment: WebQuest on implementing advanced green practices in a project.

Week 3-4: WN4 - Resilience Competences for PM

- Title: Advanced Resilience in Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Strategies and skills to enhance resilience in predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Develop advanced resilience competences for managing maintenance under stress.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, resilience assessment tools, video lectures.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: In-depth exploration of advanced resilience strategies.
 - Presentation: Key points with comprehensive storyboard.
 - Videos: In-depth resilience-focused lectures and workshops.
 - Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
 - Assessment: WebQuest on building and demonstrating advanced resilience in a complex maintenance scenario.
-

Month 3

Week 1-2: WN5 - Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competences for PM

- Title: Advanced Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Encouraging innovation and entrepreneurial thinking in predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Apply advanced innovative and entrepreneurial skills to predictive maintenance.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, innovation tools, entrepreneurship case studies, video links.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Detailed insights on fostering advanced innovation and entrepreneurship in predictive maintenance.
- Presentation: Key points from the booklet with a comprehensive storyboard.
- Videos: In-depth lectures on advanced innovation and entrepreneurship.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
- Assessment: WebQuest on integrating advanced innovation and entrepreneurship in a maintenance context.

Week 3-4: WN6 - Relearning How to Learn in a Digital Environment

- Title: Advanced Learning in the Digital Age for Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Techniques and strategies for effective learning in a digital environment.
- Learning Objective: Enhance advanced learning skills for continuous improvement in the digital age.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, digital learning tools, video tutorials.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Comprehensive guide on advanced digital learning techniques.
- Presentation: Key points from the booklet with a comprehensive storyboard.
- Videos: Advanced digital learning tutorials.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
- Assessment: WebQuest on applying advanced digital learning techniques in a predictive maintenance context.

Structure of the Predictive Maintenance course

The course is divided into six subjects (WN), each covering a specific topic and having a targeted learning objective. Each session consists of the following elements:

- A title, a description, a learning objective, a duration, a list of required resources, and a method of assessment.

- A booklet providing as much detail as possible with proper literature.
- A detailed presentation of the material depicting the key points of the booklet. A brief framework (storyboard) is also included in the material.
- A list with video links presenting the main concepts and theories related to the topic.
- A multiple-choice quiz, testing the students' understanding and retention of the topic.
- An assessment (WebQuest), requiring the students to apply the knowledge and skills acquired on the topic to a simulated situation. It also examines the critical thinking of the students.
- Peer feedback enabling the learners to give and receive constructive feedback on their projects.

The course requires a high competency level (proficiency) in the course language in conjunction with a basic understanding in data science.

Section II: Theoretical and Practical Education

Course educational outcomes

QUALIFICATION	EQF LEVEL	KNOWLEDGES	SKILLS
<p>Predictive Maintenance Course</p> <p>(Higher Education)</p>	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engineering Principles (Advanced): A foundational understanding of mechanical, electrical, and control systems is essential for developing a Maintenance Plan. • Information Technology and Cyber Systems (Advanced): Advanced knowledge in IT and cyber systems is crucial for integrating predictive maintenance with modern industrial systems. This includes understanding IoT, cloud computing, data storage, and processing, enabling effective management of data from condition monitoring tools. Developing knowledge using various programming languages (such as Python, R, Matlab) is also necessary. • Data Science and Analytics (Intermediate): Data science and analytics, including statistical analysis, machine learning, and data mining, is vital. This knowledge allows individuals to develop predictive models, analyze complex datasets, and derive insights to optimize maintenance schedules. • Industry Standards and Regulations (Advanced): Familiarity with industry standards and regulations is necessary for compliance and safety. Understanding relevant guidelines ensures that predictive maintenance activities are both effective and legally compliant. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Analytical Skills: Proficiency in conducting root cause analysis and using advanced statistical techniques to analyze maintenance data. • Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving: Ability to analyze complex systems, identify potential failure points, and develop innovative solutions. • Data Interpretation and Decision Making: Expertise in interpreting maintenance data, developing predictive models, and decision making. • Risk Assessment and Project Management: Skills in conducting risk assessments, developing mitigation strategies, and managing predictive maintenance projects efficiently.

Predictive Maintenance training program - Modules	Recommended contact hours	Estimated Workload
WN1: Holistic PM competences	10	24
WN2: Digital skills competences for PM	9	22
WN3: Green skills competences for PM	9.5	24
WN4: Resilience competences for PM	9.5	24
WN5: Innovation and entrepreneurship competences for PM	6	15
WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment	6	15
Total	50	124

Module Description

WN1 Module: Holistic PM competences

Module WN1: Holistic PM competences		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Types of Predictive Maintenance Technologies Data Acquisition and Management Integration of IoT, AI, Machine Learning and Industry 4.0 Predictive Maintenance Software and Tools Regulatory Compliance and Safety Standards Implementation Strategies, Case Studies and Real-World Applications for Predictive Maintenance Optimization Future Trends in Predictive Maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhancing Operational Efficiency of learners by utilizing various PM schemes. Enhance Critical thinking by forcing students to use new and different techniques, methodologies and tools. Boosting Project & Time management capacity of the learner. Cultivating a Continuous Learning attitude on learners. Boost Decision-making and Analytical problem-solving capabilities of the learner by acquiring new knowledge on specific topics. Boost expertise in Equipment handling & digital tools. Develop Technical writing skills by applying PM monitoring methods for administrative, financial and managerial purposes. Provide basic Algorithmic, statistical, and programming skills for PM schemes. 	10

Learning nodes of WN1 Module: Holistic PM competences

Module WN1: Holistic PM competences	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN1.1. Introduction to Maintenance Methodologies	0.5
WN1.2. Sensor Technologies & Data Analysis	1.5
WN1.3. Asset Optimization, Monitoring & Reporting Models	2
WN1.4. Structural Assessment Methods & Remote Infrastructure Management	3.5
WN1.5. Forecasting Systems	2.5
Total	10
WORKLOAD	24

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN1.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the core concepts, benefits and challenges of predictive maintenance compared to other maintenance strategies. Comparison of different main maintenance methodologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhancing Operational Efficiency of learners by utilizing various PM schemes. Cultivating a Continuous Learning attitude on learners.
WN1.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic principles, key types, future trends of Sensing Technologies plus their role in PM. Fault Detection and Diagnosis process steps. Understanding of how to implement and use IoT sensors and devices for real-time equipment monitoring. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Boost Decision-making and Analytical problem-solving capabilities of the learner by acquiring new knowledge on specific topics. Boost expertise in Equipment handling & digital tools.
WN1.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Background on time management systems used to pinpoint maintenance schedules. Estimating Remaining Useful Life (RUL). Presenting various methods and importance of monitoring & reporting process in PM. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Boosting Project & Time management capacity of the learner. Provide basic Algorithmic, statistical, and programming skills for PM schemes. Develop Technical writing skills by applying PM monitoring methods.
WN1.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commonly utilized structural assessment methods. Familiarity with popular predictive maintenance software solutions and platforms. Awareness of emerging trends and innovations in predictive maintenance, such as 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gain practical experience in technical equipment handling through automated systems and software solutions. Develop Technical writing skills by applying PM software solutions for administration activities.

	advancements in AI and machine learning, edge computing, and AR/VR.	
WN1.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Familiarity with statistical techniques and machine learning algorithms used in predictive maintenance, such as regression analysis, decision trees, neural networks, and clustering. ● Data Analysis techniques ● Reduction of Unplanned Downtime and Asset Health Management ● Cost-benefit analysis to justify predictive maintenance investments. ● Understanding of model evaluation metrics and validation techniques to ensure predictive model accuracy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Acquiring new working methods for Asset optimization & Operations scheduling to boost individual performance. ● Enhance Data Analysis & Visualization skills. ● Use of Algorithmic, statistical, and programming skills for Cost-benefit analysis and asset health management scenarios.

WN1 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards.
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Hands-on field visits from external stakeholders demonstrating PM tools and technologies in collaboration with PreMETS trainers (during project implementation will be done in 2 pilot sites; Romania & Greece).
- Project-based learning via an individual assignment (described within WebQuest document) to develop a PM plan for their company or a hypothetical organization.

WN2 Module: Digital skills competences for PM

Module WN2: Digital skills competences for PM		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-depth analysis and critical comparison of Condition-Based, Preventive, Proactive, and Predictive Maintenance strategies. • Evaluation of predictive maintenance techniques • Advanced strategies for data collection, preprocessing, and storage • Advanced examination of AI categories • Critical analysis of machine learning implementation challenges and interpretability in complex maintenance scenarios. • Strategic evaluation of cybersecurity measures and ethical considerations governing maintenance data usage • Exploration of blockchain fundamentals and its disruptive potential in ensuring immutable data integrity for maintenance operations. • Strategic insights into IoT architecture, emphasizing their role in revolutionizing predictive maintenance paradigms. • Advanced usage of project management tool selection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance Strategy Mastery • Advanced Data Analysis and Interpretation • Technology Integration and Utilization • Signal Processing and Thermography Proficiency • Model Integration and Reliability Assessment • Cybersecurity and Data Ethics Leadership • Blockchain Application Expertise • IoT Ecosystem Proficiency • Project Management Excellence 	9

Learning nodes of WN2 Module: Digital skills competences for PM

Module WN2: Digital skills competences for PM	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN2.1. Types of Maintenance & Role of Digitalisation	0.5
WN2.2. Predictive maintenance techniques and emerging technologies in PM	2

WN2.3. Data Utilisation with AI and Machine learning in Predictive Maintenance	4
WN2.4. Ethical considerations, cybersecurity and blockchain technologies	1
WN2.5. IoT Devices in PM	1
WN2.6. Project management and collaboration tools.	0.5
Total	9
WORKLOAD	22

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN2.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mastery in defining Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM), distinguishing it from Preventive Maintenance, and understanding its proactive approach in maintenance strategies. • Proficiency in Predictive Maintenance methodologies, including CBM, and the technologies utilized for effective implementation. • Comprehensive knowledge of the primary disparities between Preventive Maintenance (PM) and CBM, emphasizing the proactive nature of CBM in maintenance planning and execution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Profound grasp of Maintenance Strategies, encompassing the principles, methodologies, and approaches. • Advanced proficiency in Data Analysis Interpretation, involving the extraction, analysis. • Practical implementation of domain-specific expertise, theoretical concepts, and best practices to address maintenance challenges, optimize processes. • Comprehensive mastery of Proactive Maintenance Planning, involving the strategic identification, assessment, and mitigation of potential equipment failures.
WN2.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expertise in Predictive Maintenance techniques and methodologies. • Profound understanding of the limitations and challenges associated with Predictive Maintenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced expertise in Signal Processing Proficiency, encompassing the ability to analyze, manipulate, and interpret signals acquired from sensors and machinery to extract meaningful insights, detect anomalies, and predict equipment failures. • Advanced proficiency in Thermography Application. • In-depth understanding of Visual Inspection Techniques, involving the systematic examination of machinery and components using visual cues and inspection tools to

		<p>identify defects, anomalies, and signs of wear or damage.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced capability in Fault Prediction Interpretation. • Expertise in Real-time Monitoring, involving the continuous surveillance and analysis of equipment health and performance data in real-time.
WN2.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proficiency in assessing the quality and identifying sources of data. • Familiarity with different data collection methods and preprocessing steps. • Comprehensive knowledge of AI categories, subfields, and goals, particularly in the context of Predictive Maintenance. • Expertise in implementing AI in Predictive Maintenance, including hybrid approaches and model evaluation methods to optimize performance. • Understanding the application of machine learning (ML) in Predictive Maintenance within the framework of Industry 4.0 technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proficient in advanced data analysis techniques, including preprocessing, interpretation, and feature engineering, to extract actionable insights from raw sensor data for predictive maintenance. • Expertise in implementing IoT and sensor technologies, leveraging cloud and edge computing platforms to collect, process, and analyze real-time data for predictive maintenance applications. • Advanced proficiency in fault detection, analysis methodologies, and algorithm design tailored to specific predictive maintenance use cases. • Deep understanding of AI for robotics applications and building expert systems, facilitating autonomous maintenance tasks. • Profound knowledge of predictive maintenance strategies with AI and machine learning.
WN2.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Profound understanding of the importance of cybersecurity in Predictive Maintenance, emphasizing the safeguarding of IoT devices, networks, and data from potential cyber threats. • Proficiency in adhering to data ethics principles, ensuring responsible and ethical use of data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mastery in implementing robust cybersecurity measures to protect predictive maintenance systems from cyber threats and ensure data integrity and confidentiality. • Adherence to ethical principles in data management, including transparency, accountability, and fairness, to maintain trust and integrity in predictive maintenance operations. • Proficiency in navigating regulatory frameworks and

	<p>in Predictive Maintenance practices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expertise in navigating regulatory compliance standards relevant to Predictive Maintenance, ensuring adherence to legal and industry-specific regulations. • Comprehensive knowledge of data protection measures aimed at securing sensitive information and maintaining data integrity in Predictive Maintenance systems. • Deep understanding of Blockchain technology fundamentals, including its decentralized nature, cryptographic principles, and distributed ledger architecture. 	<p>compliance standards relevant to predictive maintenance data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expertise in safeguarding data privacy through encryption, access controls, and anonymization techniques, preserving the confidentiality of sensitive maintenance data. • Comprehensive understanding of blockchain structures and applications and identifying industry-specific blockchain use cases for enhancing maintenance operations.
WN2.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-depth knowledge of IoT Communication Technologies, spanning various protocols and standards used to facilitate communication between IoT devices and networks. • Ability to identify Applications of IoT in Various Industries. • Expertise in the Role of IoT in Predictive Maintenance, highlighting the pivotal role of IoT devices and data in enabling predictive maintenance practices for proactive asset management and optimization. • Familiarity with Cloud-Based IoT Platforms and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Profound comprehension of the IoT ecosystem and device functionalities. • Expertise in implementing robust security measures within IoT systems to mitigate cyber threats and safeguard sensitive data transmitted and stored within the IoT infrastructure. • Advanced skills in designing and deploying scalable IoT architectures tailored to specific predictive maintenance requirements. • Proficiency in analyzing IoT data streams for predictive maintenance insights.

	their role in providing scalable infrastructure.	
WN2.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognizing the paramount Importance of Project Management Tools in Predictive Maintenance. Familiarity with Commonly Used Project Management Tools. Understanding the Features and Descriptions of Project Management Tools. Appreciating the Role of Computerized Maintenance Management Systems (CMMS) in Project Management. Insight into Enterprise Asset Management (EAM) Solutions for Predictive Maintenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proficiency in identifying and selecting project management tools tailored to the unique needs of predictive maintenance initiatives. Expertise in setting up and configuring project management platforms to streamline workflows and optimize project planning and execution processes. Advanced skills in facilitating collaboration among team members and tracking project progress effectively within project management software. Utilization of Computerized Maintenance Management Systems (CMMS) for comprehensive maintenance planning and tracking. Capability to evaluate and assess enterprise-level solutions designed for predictive maintenance.

WN2 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards.
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Hands-on field visits from external stakeholders demonstrating PM tools and technologies in collaboration with PreMETS trainers (during project implementation will be done in 2 pilot sites; Romania & Greece).
- Project-based learning via an individual assignment (described within WebQuest document) to develop a PM plan for their company or a hypothetical organization.

Module WN3: Green skills competences for PM

Module WN3: Green skills competences for PM		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insight of the significant threat posed by unchecked greenhouse gas emissions and the urgency of mitigating climate change impacts. • In-depth knowledge of greenhouse gas accounting frameworks and international agreements, including the UNFCCC, Kyoto Protocol, Paris Agreement, and Greenhouse Gas Protocol. • Critical knowledge of the three scopes of GHG emissions and the complexities involved in measuring and reporting Scope 3 emissions, particularly for manufacturing companies. • Profound understanding of the importance of mitigating environmental impacts, such as GHG emissions and wastewater pollution, through sustainable manufacturing practices and innovative solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert skills in managing and reporting greenhouse gas emissions, including the ability to apply financial and cost accounting principles to address measurement challenges. • Advanced skills in innovative wastewater treatment methods, such as membrane technology and two-step pre-treatment processes, to address water scarcity and pollution issues in manufacturing processes. • Excellent skills in analyzing environmental data and reporting GHG emissions and wastewater treatment outcomes effectively to stakeholders. • Profound skills in ensuring compliance with environmental regulations and standards related to GHG emissions, wastewater treatment, and sustainability in manufacturing operations. 	9.5

Learning nodes of WN3 Module: Green skills competences for PM

Module WN3: Green skills for PM	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN3.1. Integrating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Principles in Manufacturing	1
WN3.2. Introduction to GHG Emissions, Global Agreements Corporate Accountability and Reporting	0.5
WN3.3. Life Cycle Assessment: Theory, Methods, and Practical Applications	1
WN3.4. Renewable Energy and Sustainable Manufacturing Practices	4
WN3.5. Sustainable Manufacturing and Resource Efficiency	3
Total	9.5
WORKLOAD	24

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN3.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proficient understanding of ESG Principles and their significance in modern manufacturing. • Comprehensible knowledge of environmental considerations, such as sustainable resource management, carbon footprint reduction, and waste management practices in manufacturing. • In-depth understanding of social responsibility, the importance of employee welfare, community engagement, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) in manufacturing operations. • Mastery in corporate governance and ethical 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mastery in ESG integration by identifying opportunities and strategies for integrating ESG principles into manufacturing operations. • Expertise in ESG reporting, compliance with standards, and transparent communication of ESG initiatives. • Profound skills in engaging with stakeholders to build trust, foster transparency, and communicate ESG efforts effectively. • Advanced proficiency in identifying and addressing ethical dilemmas and sustainability challenges in manufacturing. • Comprehensive understanding of the need for continuous improvement of skills in monitoring ESG performance metrics and implementing continuous improvement

	<p>business practices, and the importance of transparency and accountability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expert knowledge in ESG frameworks, reporting standards, and metrics used in manufacturing. ● Strategic Integration of ESG principles into manufacturing processes, with a focus on quality department involvement and compliance. ● Proficiency in ESG reporting, avoiding greenwashing, and using tools for accurate data collection and reporting. ● Awareness of emerging trends and innovations in ESG practices and sustainability in manufacturing. 	<p>measures to drive sustainability efforts forward.</p>
<p>WN3.2</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Profound understanding of GHG emissions in contributing to climate change and its potentially irreversible and catastrophic impacts on humanity and the environment. ● Recognize the importance of GHG accounting for corporate GHG performance, especially in ESG reports, as a top priority for organizations aiming to mitigate climate change and enhance sustainability. ● Advanced proficiency of key international agreements and frameworks such as the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the Kyoto Protocol, the Paris 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Advanced capability in innovative wastewater treatment, such as continuous adsorptive wastewater treatment and two-step pre-treatment processes, as demonstrated in the studies provided.

	<p>Agreement, and the Greenhouse Gas Protocol, which provide guidelines and standards for measuring and reporting GHG emissions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• In depth-understanding of the three scopes of GHG emissions, including direct (Scope 1), indirect (Scope 2), and other indirect emissions (Scope 3), and the associated challenges in measuring and reporting Scope 3 emissions, particularly for manufacturing companies.• Mastery in applying financial and cost accounting principles: Learners will explore the application of financial and cost accounting principles in addressing the complexities of Scope 3 emissions reporting, offering potential solutions for manufacturing companies grappling with measurement challenges.• Comprehensive knowledge of membrane technology in wastewater treatment, as a pivotal solution for addressing global water scarcity issues, its applications in wastewater treatment, and the challenges associated with the membrane fabrication process.• Excellent understanding of environmental impact mitigation, such as GHG emissions and wastewater pollution, through sustainable manufacturing practices and innovative solutions.	
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<p>WN3.3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understanding the principles and concepts of sustainable development. ● In-depth knowledge of the key components and stages of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). ● Comprehensive knowledge of different Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) methods and their applications. ● Awareness of the challenges and issues associated with LCA and Hybrid LCA methodologies. ● Knowledge of real-world case studies demonstrating the application of hybrid LCA methods. ● Understanding the benefits and limitations of utilizing LCA in various industries. ● Familiarity with specific studies mentioned in the course, such as those by Ghosh and Bakshi, and Sherwood et al. ● Awareness of software tools available for conducting LCA and their practical use. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Profound knowledge of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) principles, methodologies, and practical applications. ● Ability to apply LCA methodologies to real-world case studies and scenarios, interpreting and effectively communicating results. ● Expertise in defining and determining system boundaries in LCA models. ● Profound knowledge and expertise in assessing data quality and requirements for effective LCA modeling. ● Ability to define and determine the system boundaries in Life Cycle Assessment. ● Skills in identifying and addressing double counting incidents in Hybrid LCA methodologies. ● Capacity to assess data quality and requirement for effective LCA modeling. ● Advanced proficiency in understanding and resolving issues such as double counting incidents in Hybrid LCA methodologies. ● Advanced understanding and proficiency in utilizing LCA software tools like SimaPro and GaBi effectively.
<p>WN3.4</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expert knowledge of various renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro, and biomass. ● Awareness of the benefits and challenges associated with renewable energy adoption. ● Familiarity with advancements in solar thermal systems, photovoltaic technologies, and biomass utilization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expert skills in identifying opportunities for energy efficiency improvements in manufacturing processes. ● Mastery in implementing energy-saving strategies to reduce energy consumption and costs. ● Proficient skills in analyzing carbon footprints and developing strategies for emission reduction. ● In depth understanding and skills in interpreting policy frameworks related to renewable energy and sustainability.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Profound understanding of the concept of electrification and its application in industrial processes. ● Knowledge of strategies and techniques for enhancing energy efficiency in manufacturing operations. ● Deep understanding of the importance of energy-efficient practices and their impact on sustainability. ● Expertise in carbon footprints and methods for reducing emissions in manufacturing processes. ● Proficiency in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and its role in evaluating environmental impacts throughout the product life cycle. ● Comprehensive knowledge of the economic benefits associated with adopting renewable energy in manufacturing. ● Profound understanding of policy frameworks and regulations supporting renewable energy integration and sustainability initiatives. ● Practical knowledge of implementing renewable energy solutions in manufacturing plants. ● Analysis of real-world case studies showcasing successful transitions to renewable energy in various industries. ● Proficiency in emerging technologies and future directions in renewable energy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Skillful in ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and standards in manufacturing operations. ● Proficient skills in planning and executing renewable energy projects in manufacturing facilities. ● Comprehensive ability to manage resources effectively and coordinate stakeholders to achieve sustainability goals. ● Excellence in analyzing complex issues related to renewable energy integration and sustainability in manufacturing. ● Expertise in developing innovative solutions to address challenges and optimize processes for sustainability. ● Ability to effectively communicate sustainability initiatives and project plans to stakeholders.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive knowledge of the role of renewable energy in achieving global sustainability goals. 	
WN3.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of environmental challenges faced by industries, such as energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, pollution, and resource depletion. • Knowledge of sustainable practices that organizations can employ to enhance resource efficiency and reduce environmental impact, including mass balance, full-cost accounting, product life cycle assessment, systematic engineering processes, extended producer responsibility (EPR), and product life-cycle value design. • Awareness of innovative research methods, like Resources Value Mapping, which maps and categorizes activities based on lean philosophy principles to enhance energy and resource efficiency. • Understanding of Circular Economy: They will gain an understanding of the concept of a recirculation-based society and its emphasis on minimizing intake and output from nature, leading to reduced environmental impact. • Expert knowledge of sustainable manufacturing technologies, such as biomass, solar thermal systems, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced skills in sustainable decision-making by considering the environmental, social, and economic aspects of manufacturing processes, thereby contributing to the broader goals of sustainability and resource efficiency.

	<p>electrification, and their potential to contribute to sustainable resource management and environmental objectives.</p>	
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WN3 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topic-learning nodes), +50 slides of content summary provided for asynchronous learning.
- A detailed booklet for self-paced reading.
- Project-based learning via an individual WebQuest assignment.
- Assessment tool with 5 multiple choice questions, explanations and answers.
- Comprehensive and illustrative storyboards.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic-learning node.

WN4 Module: Resilience competencies for PM

Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core Principles and Benefits of Predictive Maintenance (PM) • Role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in PM • Risk Assessment Methodologies and Mitigation Strategies • Human Safety Systems in Maintenance Operations • Adapting to Technological Changes and Continuous Improvement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of AI and Machine Learning Algorithms • Risk Assessment and Mitigation Strategy Development • Adaptability and Problem-Solving • Effective Communication and Continuous Learning skills • Utilization of Advanced Monitoring Tools and Forecasting Analytics 	9.5

Learning nodes of WN4 Module: Resilience competencies for PM

Module WN4: Resilience competencies for PM	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN4.1. Core Principles and Strategic Resilience in Predictive Maintenance	1
WN4.2. Advanced Technological Integration in Maintenance	3.5
WN4.3. Safety, Risk Assessment, and Structural Integrity	1
WN4.4. Competencies for Maintenance Professionals	1
WN4.5. Future Trends and Professional Development in Predictive Maintenance	3.0
Total	9.5
WORKLOAD	24

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN4.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understand the foundational concepts and benefits of Predictive Maintenance (PM). ● Recognize the significance of resilience competences (RC) in maintaining continuous operations. ● Explain the strategic importance of integrating a resilient approach in enterprise architecture. ● Discuss the impact of PM on reducing operational risks and optimizing resources. ● Identify strategies for continuous improvement and adaptation in maintenance practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Articulate the core principles of PM and resilience competences. ● Evaluate the effectiveness of maintenance strategies in the context of resilience. ● Develop strategic solutions to improve operational performance and safety. ● Analyze case studies to understand the practical implications of PM. ● Implement continuous improvement initiatives in maintenance operations

WN4.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in automating maintenance processes. • Learn about the application of IoT devices and sensors in real-time monitoring. • Explore the significance of advanced monitoring tools in predictive maintenance. • Gain knowledge on the use of forecasting analytics in predicting maintenance needs. • Recognize the importance of data integration and analysis for proactive maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement AI and ML algorithms to analyze maintenance data and predict failures. • Utilize IoT devices for real-time data collection and monitoring. • Apply advanced monitoring tools to enhance predictive maintenance strategies. • Develop and use forecasting models to anticipate maintenance requirements. • Integrate various data sources to improve maintenance decision-making
WN4.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the importance of human safety systems in maintenance operations. • Learn about various risk assessment tools and their applications in proactive maintenance. • Gain knowledge on structural assessment techniques like NDT and SHM. • Recognize the methods for identifying safety hazards in maintenance. • Explore strategies for effective risk mitigation and management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement safety systems and protocols in maintenance tasks. • Conduct thorough risk assessments using tools like FMEA, HAZOP and RCA. • Perform structural assessments to identify potential equipment issues. • Develop effective risk mitigation strategies to prevent failures. • Apply best practices for maintaining safety and minimizing hazards in maintenance operations.
WN4.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the significance of adaptability and problem-solving in maintenance roles. • Learn about the importance of technical proficiency and stress management. • Recognize the value of effective communication and teamwork. • Gain knowledge on fostering a continuous learning mindset. • Explore the role of attention to detail and effective time management in maintenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapt quickly to changes and solve complex maintenance issues effectively. • Demonstrate technical expertise in handling and maintaining equipment. • Communicate clearly and concisely with team members and stakeholders. • Foster a culture of continuous learning and professional development. • Manage time efficiently to adhere to maintenance schedules and priorities.

WN4.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the anticipated technological changes and their impact on predictive maintenance. • Recognize the evolving skills requirements for staying competitive in the maintenance field. • Learn about the integration of sustainability and ethical considerations in maintenance practices. • Explore the importance of fostering innovation and adaptability in maintenance operations. • Identify strategies for continuous learning and collaboration with educational institutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapt to new technologies and methodologies in predictive maintenance. • Identify and develop skills that align with future industry trends. • Incorporate sustainability and ethical considerations in maintenance strategies. • Foster a culture of innovation and strategic thinking to address future challenges. • Collaborate with educational and research institutions for continuous professional development.
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WN4 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics-learning nodes), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for asynchronous learning.
- A comprehensive booklet for self-paced reading incorporating a large list of references.
- Project-based learning via an individual WebQuest assignment.
- Assessment tool with 5 multiple choice questions, explanations and answers.
- Comprehensive and illustrative storyboards.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic-learning node.

WN5 Module: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM

Module WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Types of Predictive Maintenance Technologies • Integration of IoT and Industry 4.0 in PM • Fundamentals of Innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultivate an Innovative & Entrepreneurial Mindset to the learners by teaching and utilizing new approaches during the course module. 	6

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Creativity, Adaptability and Problem-Solving Skills ● Entrepreneurial Mindset in Predictive Maintenance ● Fundamentals in Marketing & Branding ● Future Trends in Predictive Maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Boost Project management capabilities of the learner with focus on marketing and corporate communication activities. ● Critical thinking, Creativity & Adaptability methods for managerial applications in a working environment. ● Cultivating a Continuous Learning attitude on learners. ● Utilize new Project & Time management techniques. ● Enhance Strategic analysis capabilities by learning and utilizing various software tools and methodologies. ● Promote collaboration and teamwork schemes for effective analysis and decision-making. 	
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Learning nodes of WN5 Module: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM

Module WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN5.1. Recap on PM methods and strategies	2
WN5.2. Fundamentals of Innovation & Entrepreneurial Mindset in Predictive Maintenance	1
WN5.3. Marketing and Branding Strategies	1.5
WN5.4. Creativity, Adaptability and Problem-Solving Skills	0.5
WN5.5. Latest Developments and Trends in PM	1
Total	6
WORKLOAD	15

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN5.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Predictive Maintenance: History, Traditional Practices & Advancements ● Traditional vs Predictive Practices ● Predictive Maintenance in the Industry 4.0 Era ● Challenges in Adopting Predictive Maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cultivating a Continuous Learning attitude on learners. ● Recap on basic Algorithmic, statistical, and programming skills necessary for IoT and Industry 4.0 applications in PM.
WN5.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Innovative Approaches to Predictive Maintenance ● 4 different types of Innovation ● Entrepreneurial Mindset & Opportunities in Predictive Maintenance ● Successful PM application steps ● SWOT Analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cultivate an Innovative & Entrepreneurial Mindset to the learners by teaching and utilizing new approaches during the course module. ● Utilize new Project & Time management techniques. ● Use of Algorithmic, statistical, and programming skills for stakeholder capacity, business/market analysis and project management implementation plans.
WN5.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Essentials of Marketing & Branding in Predictive Maintenance ● Campaign Creation Guide steps ● Post-Campaign Analysis ● Market Dynamics & Customer Needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Boost Project management capabilities of the learner with focus on marketing and corporate communication activities. ● Capitalize various marketing and branding techniques to find solutions through Analytical problem-solving.
WN5.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adaptive Thinking principles ● Implementation tips & Market Analysis in PM ● 4 different types of Innovation ● Fundamentals of problem solving ● Creativity techniques 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Capitalize innovative business schemes to idealize new strategic analysis and project management strategies. ● Promote collaboration and teamwork schemes for effective analysis and decision-making. ● Boost Analytical problem-solving capabilities of the learner by acquiring new knowledge on specific topics. ● Enhance Presentation skills by transferring acquired knowledge to co-workers through creative tools.

WN5.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI and IoT: Revolutionizing Predictive Maintenance • Machine Learning in Predictive Maintenance • Case Studies & Best practices • Future Trends in Predictive Maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bring awareness on future trends and cultivate a lifelong learning attitude. • Boost Project management capabilities of the learner with focus on marketing and corporate communication activities.
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WN5 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards.
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Project-based learning via a group assessment assignment (described within WebQuest document) to idealize and develop a PM project together with team members.

WN6 Module: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment

Module WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key characteristics and comparison of online and traditional classroom settings. • Predictive maintenance applications in different industrial environments. • Differentiation in learning process preferences of individuals. • Understanding the importance of combining traditional and modern instructional methods. • Active learning strategies and their valuable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to adjust to different formats and methodologies in online learning. • Creating and adhering to a study plan. • Selecting and utilizing technical resources. • Incorporating real-life projects, internships, or industry collaborations • Developing and implementing predictive maintenance systems • Adapting Teaching Methods: Developing diverse teaching 	6

contribution to digital learning environments.	<p>strategies to accommodate various learning preferences.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analytical skills to assess the effectiveness of different learning strategies Active engagement and participation in eLearning Collaboration and teamwork skills developed through group projects and peer review sessions. Digital literacy and proficiency in using collaborative platforms 	
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Learning nodes of WN6 Module: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment

Module WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN6.1. Learning environment	2
WN6.2. Personal Learning Environment	1
WN6.3. Student Typology	0.5
WN6.4. Student Profiles	0.5
WN6.5. Pedagogical framework	1
WN6.6. Active Learning	1
Total	6
WORKLOAD	15

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN6.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding differences between online and traditional classroom settings. Versatility of online education in content presentation and assessment. Inclusivity and broad-reaching approach of online learning. Benefits and challenges of asynchronous and synchronous learning. Key traits required for success in online learning environments. Key characteristics of successful online learners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to adjust to different formats and methodologies in online learning. Creating and adhering to a study plan. Managing schedules without in-person reminders. Seeking help when needed and participating in discussions through digital platforms. Navigating online learning platforms and utilizing various digital tools. Overcoming technical issues and maintaining daily engagement with coursework. Studying and completing assignments independently.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Setting and achieving educational goals without direct supervision. ● Establishing a quiet, dedicated space for studying. ● Engaging with recorded sessions and revisiting material as revision before assessments. ● Contributing to online forums and discussion groups, sharing perspectives, and seeking clarification. ● Recognizing the value of online learning and learning from the experiences of others in a virtual setting.
WN6.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Concept of a Personal Learning Environment (PLE) in the context of predictive maintenance. ● Components of a PLE, including technical resources, online learning platforms, software tools, communities, and practical experiences. ● Implementation and benefits of predictive maintenance in various sectors like urban mass transit, construction, and bridge health monitoring. ● Application of predictive analytics and data mining techniques in structural health monitoring. ● Integration of multi-dimensional analysis with fuzzy logic in construction project management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Selecting and utilizing technical resources such as journals, eBooks, and specialized websites for predictive maintenance. ● Engaging with online learning platforms (e.g., Coursera, edX) to acquire knowledge and skills in predictive maintenance. ● Gaining hands-on experience with software tools like MATLAB and predictive maintenance platforms. ● Participating in online forums and professional networks to exchange knowledge and collaborate with peers and experts. ● Incorporating real-life projects, internships, or industry collaborations for practical experience in predictive maintenance. ● Using self-reflection tools like learning diaries or blogs to document progress and reflect on learning processes. ● Applying data analytics, machine learning, and sensor technology for predictive maintenance in real-world scenarios. ● Developing and implementing predictive maintenance systems to improve operational reliability and reduce maintenance costs.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employing a hybrid multi-dimensional fuzzy-based approach for risk assessment and management in construction projects. • Utilizing predictive analytics and data mining techniques for assessing and improving the structural performance of bridges through SHM data.
WN6.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learner Typology in Engineering and Predictive Maintenance: Understanding how different learners prefer to receive information and process it. • VARK Model: Visual, Aural, Read/Write, and Kinesthetic learning preferences. • Sensory Modalities: Recognizing that individuals have diverse preferences for learning, including visual, auditory, read/write, and kinesthetic. • Predictive Maintenance (PdM) in Engineering: Proactive approach using data analysis tools to detect anomalies and predict equipment failures. • Training Methods for Predictive Maintenance: Incorporating theoretical learning, hands-on practice, and technology utilization in training programs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying Learning Preferences: Assessing individual learning styles to tailor educational approaches effectively. • Adapting Teaching Methods: Developing diverse teaching strategies to accommodate various learning preferences. • Utilizing Data Analysis Tools: Proficiency in using data analysis software and machine learning algorithms. • Hands-on Experience with Sensor Technology: Practical skills in installing, monitoring, and interpreting data from sensors. • Navigation of Predictive Maintenance Software: Ability to navigate and utilize specialized software for predictive maintenance. • Analyzing Case Studies and Simulations: Critical thinking skills in analyzing real-world examples and engaging in simulated scenarios. • Workshop Facilitation: Conducting workshops on data analysis techniques essential for predictive maintenance. • Online Course Development: Creating online courses on IoT technologies applied in predictive maintenance. • Software Training: Providing training sessions on predictive maintenance software solutions. • Seminar Presentation: Delivering presentations on case studies of

		successful predictive maintenance implementations.
WN6.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the learning preferences of visual, aural, read/write, and kinesthetic learners in science and engineering. • Familiarity with visual learning strategies, including the use of diagrams, simulations, and visual data representation techniques. • Knowledge of auditory learning techniques, such as listening to lectures, podcasts, and engaging in group discussions. • Understanding read/write learning strategies. • Awareness of kinesthetic learning preferences and strategies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proficiency in implementing visual learning strategies through the use of visual aids, video content, mind maps, and interactive simulations. • Applying read/write learning strategies, including note-taking, summarizing, creating flashcards, and participating in online forums. • Capability to engage kinesthetic learners through lab experiments, interactive learning tools, physical movement integration, and practical projects. • Adaptability in incorporating various teaching methods to accommodate different learning preferences effectively. • Analytical skills to assess the effectiveness of different learning strategies and adjust teaching approaches accordingly. • Proficiency in utilizing technology-enhanced learning tools and platforms to support diverse learning styles and preferences.
WN6.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the pedagogical framework's emphasis on blending traditional and modern instructional methods for teaching predictive maintenance. • Recognition of the importance of acquiring general knowledge for developing skills in predictive maintenance. • Appreciation for the role of pedagogical frameworks in structuring effective teaching and learning strategies, even 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proficiency in hands-on activities such as analyzing machine performance data and conducting vibration analysis. • Ability to apply theoretical concepts in real-world contexts through reflection and experiential learning. • Competence in using digital tools and resources for learning, including simulation software and online platforms. • Skill in pre-learning at home and applying knowledge in class, honing time management and self-directed learning capabilities.

	<p>in specialized fields like predictive maintenance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Familiarity with the Constructivist Learning Theory. ● Awareness of Technology-Enhanced Learning (TEL). ● Understanding the Flipped Classroom Model. ● Understanding of Problem-Based Learning (PBL). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proficiency in teamwork and collaboration through group projects, developing communication and interpersonal skills. ● Capability to solve real-world problems through problem-based learning, fostering creativity and innovation in addressing complex challenges. ● Competency in interpreting data and making informed decisions, crucial for predictive maintenance tasks and ensuring efficient operations.
WN6.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understanding of active learning strategies and their transformative impact on eLearning. ● Familiarity with Edward de Bono's Six Thinking Hats method and its application in problem-solving and creative thinking. ● Knowledge of the six metaphorical hats and their respective perspectives in problem-solving. ● Awareness of the importance of sequential or predetermined order in using the Six Thinking Hats method. ● Insight into the integration of simulations, case studies, and virtual labs to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills in eLearning. ● Understanding of collaborative platforms and project-based learning to foster collaboration and practical skill application. ● Awareness of reflective practices such as reflection journals and e-portfolios for deepening learning and personal growth. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Active engagement and participation in eLearning through active learning strategies. ● Critical thinking and problem-solving skills enhanced by applying the Six Thinking Hats method. ● Collaboration and teamwork skills developed through group projects and peer review sessions. ● Digital literacy and proficiency in using collaborative platforms like Google Workspace and Microsoft Teams. ● Practical skill application through project-based learning and digital maker spaces. ● Reflective practice skills through maintaining reflection journals and e-portfolios. ● Effective self-assessment skills in predictive maintenance. ● Ability to seek feedback and mentorship for self-assessment and professional development. ● Proficiency in creating and utilizing Skills Maps for personal and professional development. ● Self-awareness and self-improvement skills through tools like Bloom's Taxonomy, Johari Window Model, and 360-degree feedback.

WN6 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 47 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards.
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Hands-on field visits from external stakeholders demonstrating PM tools and technologies in collaboration with PreMETS trainers (during project implementation will be done in 2 pilot sites; Romania & Greece).
- Project-based learning via an individual assignment (described within WebQuest document) to develop a PM plan for their company or a hypothetical organization.

Section III: Examination and Qualification

Examination Planning

The examination objectives are designed to align seamlessly with the PreMETS Predictive Maintenance course's EQF level 7 compliant learning outcomes across various modules:

- WN1: Holistic PM Competences
- WN2: Digital Skills Competences for PM
- WN3: Green Skills Competences for PM
- WN4: Resilience Competences for PM
- WN5: Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competences for PM
- WN6: Relearning How to Learn in a Digital Environment

Each module will employ appropriate digital assessment formats, such as multiple-choice questions for factual knowledge.

- 5 questions from the WP2 assessment questionnaire will be training questions and tasks will be developed to test both theoretical understanding and practical application.
- 25 questions (WP2) that are diverse and inclusive, catering to different learning styles and digital proficiency levels will be used as assessment and certification questions.

PreMETS microcredential certifications are tailored around the Europass Digital Credentials framework to take these EU instruments to the next pan-EU level.

PreMETS' micro-credential modules are linked to the ECTS level 7 courses.

PreMETS Digital Certificate will be issued.

Course Objective:

To equip advanced learners with in-depth knowledge and expertise in preventive maintenance, enabling them to design, implement, and optimize preventive maintenance programs, utilize advanced digital tools, and lead maintenance teams effectively.

Examination Objectives:

1. Advanced Maintenance Strategies:
 - Explain advanced preventive maintenance strategies and their implementation.
 - Analyze the cost-benefit of preventive maintenance versus other maintenance strategies.
2. Designing Maintenance Programs:
 - Develop a comprehensive preventive maintenance program for a complex facility.
 - Integrate sustainability and green practices into preventive maintenance planning.

3. Utilizing Advanced Digital Tools:
 - Demonstrate proficiency in using advanced maintenance management software.
 - Analyze maintenance data using digital tools and predictive analytics to improve maintenance practices.
4. Leadership and Team Management:
 - Exhibit leadership skills in managing a maintenance team.
 - Develop training programs for maintenance personnel to ensure adherence to best practices.
5. Safety, Compliance, and Risk Management:
 - Formulate advanced safety protocols and compliance strategies.
 - Conduct risk assessments and implement mitigation strategies in preventive maintenance.
6. Optimization and Continuous Improvement:
 - Apply principles of continuous improvement to enhance preventive maintenance practices.
 - Use data-driven approaches to optimize maintenance schedules and reduce downtime.
7. Assessment Methods:
 - Case studies and scenario-based exams to assess the ability to design and implement maintenance programs.
 - Leadership and team management exercises, including role-playing and peer assessments.
 - Research projects or dissertations on innovative preventive maintenance techniques.
 - Comprehensive oral exams or presentations to demonstrate in-depth understanding and communication skills.

Examination Scheduling

Examinations will be available online, on the PreMETS platform after the completion of each module.

Specific time limits for different sections of the exam will be defined based on their complexity and the expected time required for completion.

Examination Administration

PreMETS platform will be used for learning and examination purposes. It includes a reliable Learning Management System (LMS) and hosts a specialized examination software that was developed under the micro credential certification framework task. It will be utilized to support secure test-taking, question randomization, and time management. As well as automated certification or re-examination process.

Detailed instructions about the examination process, rules, and technical requirements will be provided prior to the exam on the PreMETS platform.

A clear protocol for trainees to report and resolve issues during the examination will be established, including contingency plans for extended time or rescheduling if technical problems occur, all information will be public on the platform.

Examination Execution and Processes

Digital submissions will be automatically generated, collected and secured within the LMS from the PreMETS platform.

Data will be backed up and protected against unauthorized access.

Automated tools will be used for objective questions, and detailed rubrics will be provided for subjective assessments to ensure consistency and fairness in grading.

Post-training monitoring recommendations and continuous learning suggestions will be provided.

Results compilation and distribution

Results will be analyzed to identify trends, areas for improvement, and achievements.

Analytics tools provided by the LMS will be used to assess performance comprehensively.

A PreMETS Digital Certificate will be prepared and distributed through the LMS, verifying successful course completion and mastery of specific skills.

Evaluation of Results

Both written and practical examinations (where applicable) will be conducted for the award of the applicable PreMETS Predictive Maintenance Digital Certificate.

Feedback from trainees will be collected to help improve the course and teaching process.

A questionnaire will be developed and given to trainees at the end of the course to collect their opinions and impressions on the competences and knowledge acquired, as well as to identify possible areas for improvement.

Participants in the training program are eligible to take the examination if they can demonstrate attendance of at least 70% of the lessons. Participants who achieve 70% correct answers will be granted the PreMETS Predictive Maintenance Digital Certificate.

Written Examination:

For each module, the written examination will consist of multiple-choice questions, with a minimum of one question per recommended teaching hour.

Each question will have one correct answer among three proposed answers, and candidates will have between 1 and 5 minutes to answer each question, depending on its complexity.

Evaluation Performance:

To pass a Module's examination, candidates must achieve at least 70% of the maximum possible mark.

Re-examination:

Failure in any individual module of the examination will require re-examination only if the module failed. Candidates who fail any module three times must retake the classes (videos and training materials) and the examination of the failed micro-credential module.

Appendix I: EQF Framework

EQF Level	Knowledge	Skills	Responsibility and Autonomy
	<i>In the context of EQF, knowledge is described as theoretical and/or factual</i>	<i>In the context of EQF, skills are described as cognitive (involving the use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking) and practical (involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments)</i>	<i>In the context of the EQF responsibility and autonomy is described as the ability of the learner to apply knowledge and skills autonomously and with responsibility</i>
8	Knowledge at the most advanced frontier of a field of work or study and at the interface between fields	The most advanced and specialised skills and techniques, including synthesis and evaluation, required to solve critical problems in research and/or innovation and to extend and redefine existing knowledge or professional practice	Demonstrate substantial authority, innovation, autonomy, scholarly and professional integrity and sustained commitment to the development of new ideas or processes at the forefront of work or study contexts including research
7	Highly specialised knowledge, some of which is at the forefront of knowledge in a field of work or study, as the basis for original thinking and/or research Critical awareness of knowledge issues in a field and at the interface between different fields	Specialised problem-solving skills required in research and/or innovation in order to develop new knowledge and procedures and to integrate knowledge from different fields	Manage and transform work or study contexts that are complex, unpredictable and require new strategic approaches; take responsibility for contributing to professional knowledge and practice and/or for reviewing the strategic performance of teams
6	Advanced knowledge of a field of work or study, involving a critical understanding of theories and principles	Advanced skills, demonstrating mastery and innovation, required to solve complex and unpredictable problems in a specialised field of work or study	Manage complex technical or professional activities or projects, taking responsibility for decision-making in unpredictable work or study contexts; take responsibility for managing professional development of individuals and groups
5	Comprehensive, specialised, factual and theoretical knowledge within a field of work or study and an awareness of the boundaries of that knowledge	A comprehensive range of cognitive and practical skills required to develop creative solutions to abstract problems	Exercise management and supervision in contexts of work or study activities where there is unpredictable change; review and develop performance of self and others
4	Factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts within a field of work or study	A range of cognitive and practical skills required to generate solutions to specific problems in a field of work or study	Exercise self-management within the guidelines of work or study contexts that are usually predictable, but are subject to change; supervise the routine work of others, taking some responsibility for the evaluation and improvement of work or study activities
3	Knowledge of facts, principles, processes and general concepts, in a field of work or study	A range of cognitive and practical skills required to accomplish tasks and solve problems by selecting and applying basic methods, tools, materials and information	Take responsibility for completion of tasks in work or study; adapt own behaviour to circumstances in solving problems
2	Basic factual knowledge of a field of work or study	Basic cognitive and practical skills required to use relevant information in order to carry out tasks and to solve routine problems using simple rules and tools	Work or study under supervision with some autonomy
1	Basic general knowledge	Basic skills required to carry out simple tasks	Work or study under direct supervision in a structured context

Description of the eight EQF levels - <https://europass.europa.eu/en/description-eight-eqf-levels>

Figure 1: Description of EQF levels. [Online: Available: <https://europass.europa.eu/en/description-eight-eqf-levels>]

Appendix II: D2.4 – PM training toolkit higher education certification strategy language translations

D2.4 – PM training toolkit higher education certification strategy report has been translated in Romanian, Greek, Italian, German, Dutch and Serbian. A link to these translated documents can be found below.

D2.4 – PM training toolkit higher education certification strategy (Language translations)

Link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1kfK_Kq9Wx1KaUa20sT4SFGyh6Npphtzw?usp=drive_link

PreMETS

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An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

Co-funded by
the European Union

Project: 101108469 — PreMETS — ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.